

THE INFLUENCE OF PSYCHO-SOCIAL FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMORBID CONDITIONS.

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Abstract: It is known that chronic stress can lead to the development of various diseases or aggravate an existing disease. This article provides information about the influence of psychosocial factors in the development of comorbid conditions.

Key words: Stress, cortisol immunity, visceral fat, Depression, Distress.

Stress is the human body's response to excessive tension, negative emotions or simply boredom. During stress, the human body produces adrenaline, a hormone that prompts the search for a solution. A small amount of stress is necessary for everyone, because it encourages a person to think, to find a way out of a problem, without stress life would be boring. On the other hand, if there is too much stress, the body becomes weak, weak and loses its ability to solve problems.

Stress plays a major role in the development of diseases such as obesity, heart disease, Alzheimer's disease, diabetes, depression, digestive problems and asthma. In fact, stress can be a very strong innate or acquired protective reaction of the body, during which the hormones adrenaline and cortisol are produced. It is these stress hormones that make the heart beat faster, constrict blood vessels, affect breathing, and improve blood flow to muscles, lungs, and other internal organs. This puts the body collectively in a "fight or flight" mode. If stress becomes chronic, these physiological changes can lead to health problems.

How does stress affect health?

Because the stress hormone cortisol inhibits immune cells, prolonged stress and excess cortisol can weaken the immune system, resulting in frequent colds in the body.

Heart diseases. It has long been known that people with chronic stress and anxiety are more likely than others to develop cardiovascular disease (high blood pressure being the most common). Stress can increase heart rate and increase triglyceride cholesterol levels. It is known that stress is often associated with smoking and overweight, which indirectly increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases. Sudden emotional stress can lead to serious heart

diseases, including heart attacks. People with chronic heart disease should avoid stress and learn to manage it as much as possible.

Asthma. Many studies have shown that stress can make asthma worse. Some evidence suggests that chronic parental stress increases the risk of asthma in children. **Overweight and obesity.** Excess fat in the abdomen (visceral fat) is considered more dangerous than fat in the arms, legs or other parts of the body. Unfortunately, compared to healthy people, people with chronic stress suffer the most from abdominal (visceral) fat. Stress increases the level of cortisol, which indirectly contributes to the accumulation of fat around the organs.

Type 2 diabetes. Stress can worsen diabetes in two ways. First, it increases the likelihood of consuming junk food and excessive amounts of alcohol. Second, the sensitivity of cells to insulin (a hormone released by the pancreas to lower blood sugar) decreases, and blood sugar levels rise. **Headache.** Stress is a common cause of headaches, not just headaches or migraines.

Feelings of depression and anxiety. It's no surprise that chronic stress is linked to depression and anxiety. A recent study found that people who experience stress at work (such as feeling underpaid for the work they do) are 80% more likely to develop depression than those with low levels of stress.

Digestive problems. It is known that stomach or duodenal ulcers can appear against the background of stress. Also, stress can lead to exacerbation of chronic diseases of the intestinal tract, gastritis, inflammation of the intestines, and reflux. Irritable bowel syndrome is more common in people with high levels of stress.

Aging and death. There is evidence that stress can accelerate aging. People with chronic stress lose 9-17 years of life, age faster and die earlier. Managing and dealing with stress is great, but the hardest part is taking the first step. It is not always possible to remove the cause of stress from life, but you can try to change your attitude.

Several scientific studies have been devoted to this problem. The mechanisms of stress have been studied in detail and are very complex: they are related to our hormonal, nervous and vascular systems.

In some cases, the definition of "stress" refers to the trigger itself. For example, physical - this is severe cold or unbearable heat, decrease or increase in atmospheric pressure. Under the concept of chemical stress, the effect of all toxic substances is understood. Mental stress can be the result of extremely negative or positive emotions. Injuries, viral diseases, muscle overload are biological stress.

Depending on the result, the following types of stress are distinguished in psychology:

Eustresses ("beneficial" stresses). We all need a certain amount of stress to live successfully. This is the main factor of our development. This condition can be called "awakening reaction". It is like waking up from sleep. To go to work in the morning, you must first get out of bed and wake up. To achieve work activity, you need a boost - a small dose of adrenaline. Eustress performs exactly these tasks.

Distresses (harmful stresses) occur in acute stress. This type of stress represents the stress that everyone understands.

Causes of stress. The cause of stress can actually be anything that affects and disturbs a person. For example, external causes can include anxiety caused by something (change of job, death of a relative). Internal causes of stress include life values and beliefs. This includes a personal assessment

Stress and depression can occur in approximately equal proportions in women and men. However, each organism has its own characteristics. If you notice symptoms that may indicate stress, you should first identify the cause of the condition. It is much easier to eliminate the causes of stress than the consequences. It is not a lie that "all diseases are caused by nerves". Clinical observations have shown that small stresses are not harmful to the body, even beneficial. They encourage a person to find a way out of the current situation. Each of us should educate ourselves and develop our will so that depression does not turn into a more serious and long-term form. Many people are used to fight against stress with the help of antidepressants and alcohol. However, choosing such a path leads to getting used to them and not being able to give them up without expert help.

Treatment and prevention of stress. As everyone knows, there is no better medicine than good sleep. Therefore, you should think about how you sleep. Here are some tips to help you sleep better. Regular exercise is a big help for normal sleep. It is recommended to do them two hours before going to bed, in the open air. Before going to sleep, you can take a hot bath and listen to quiet music. Try to do this every day. In order for sleep to be normal and healthy, the body needs a hormone called melatonin. It increases after the intake of B group vitamins, and this vitamin is abundant in rice, wheat, barley, pistachio seeds, dried apricots. The bedroom should not be noisy and bright, these interfere with a peaceful sleep. will give.

References.

1. E. Ghaziyev "Psychology" book 2018.
2. Ziyonet
3. Khaidarov F., Joraev N. Is it easy to maintain stress or mental balance? -T., 1997.
4. Gamezo M.V., Domashenko I.A. Atlas of psychology. M., 2002
5. Psychology.uz